

FIRST DAUGHTERS' MARRIAGE RITES: A SOCIO-ANTHROPOLOGICAL VIEW IN IKOT OKU IKONO, UYO, AKWA IBOM STATE

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Abstract

Important milestones in some societies are marked by ritualistic ceremonies and the path through life of individuals is monitored and highly celebrated. A variety of communities in Nigeria practice marriage as a significant rite of passage and ritual actions are engaged as expressive and symbolic enactments of the transformations. This qualitative study examines the social, cultural, symbolic and psychological significance of first daughters' marriage in Ikot Oku Ikono Community in Akwa Ibom State. The study findings show that first daughters are seen as prized items by both parents and the entire members of the community, and their separation through marriage carries a connotation of loss. Prospective husband to a first daughter is culturally expected to adhere to the specified rituals to mark the transition. The socio-anthropological findings are relevant for contemporary understanding of the complex web of rituals relating to first daughters' marriage in the study area. The study also reveals that Christian evangelization and re-socialisation have triggered changes that threaten the cultural system in the community. The study concludes that marriage is a community affair and could only be strengthened and legitimated through participation in various ritual activities.

Keywords: First daughter, marital rites, ritual actions and socio-anthropological

Introduction

Different societies within the continent of Africa possess rich and varied cultures that shape the way individuals behave and act (Olupana, 2014). The role of culture is especially significant because it touches on all aspects of life such as health-seeking behaviour, economic activities, religious practices and marriage. In most of these societies, the world is viewed culturally as one sacred reality where there is no division between sacred and secular (Gehman, 2005). Thus, individual's path through life is monitored, marked and celebrated from birth to death (Oduyoye, 2004). However, this is especially important because of deep concern that members of the community do not develop into responsible community-oriented adults except they are socialized and initiated into the community. During the process of initiation, they undergo a set of rites which mark passing from one phase in life to another. The focal point of this paper is marriage as a unique cultural experience and sacred reality.

Generally, African marriage, unlike what is obtainable in Europe, is a complex institution that proceeds by stages and are characterized by the performance of some prescribed rites. In Nigeria, a variety of communities practice marriage as a significant rite of passage. There exist many customary marriage practices each with a sequence of rituals, negotiations and symbolic transactions. Studies (for example Oduyoye, 1992) affirm that in some societies in Africa, there is a view that married people are social adults. This implies that marriage marks an important transition from one social category to another. At another level, it implies that marriage is a community activity. In this way, the

traditional marriage rituals express these understandings (Phiri, 2011).

Ibibio culture is a repository of traditions, norms, values and social thought. These traditions, despite Western influence, continue to direct social relations in contemporary times. Ikot Oku Ikono, fondly called “IkonoUyo”, an Ibibio-speaking community has a rich cultural heritage. The people of the community place a high premium on first daughters. They are described in deeply contextual terms such as “adiaha-usen” (Lovely daughter), *eyen ukpono* (child of honour) amongst others. The coming of age of first daughters in this community is considered great gain and the social value remains sacrosanct. The culture provides for a ritual passage from singlehood to married life for first daughters. Hence for a first daughter to be considered properly married by a man, these rites must be solemnly performed. Against this backdrop, this present study presents a socio-anthropological view of these marriage rites.

Ethnography of Ikot Oku Ikono

The people and geographical location

The Ikot Oku Ikono is an Ibibio-speaking community. Generally, Ibibio are one of the oldest Benue-Bantu tribes of Sub-Saharan African (Noah, 1980). The people reached their present location via two major migratory directions. While one group reached present location through sea route, the other migrated along the overland route. The community is situated in the west of Uyo, nearby to Mbiabong and IkotNtuen with geographical coordinates: 5°0'0” North, 7°51'0”. In the pre-colonial period, the people of the community, just like other Ibibio-speaking groups, were largely rural dwellers.

Economic Life of the People

The Ibibio pre-colonial economy in general was basically a subsistence economy which depended on land (Udo, 1983). The main occupation of the people of the community was farming. Although westernization has engendered significant changes in the community such that many people have engaged in all manner of professional careers to earn a living, a good number of people still engage in traditional occupation. Food crops cultivated include Udia (Yam), Ukom (Plantain), Ibokpot (Maize), Ikpong (Coco-yam) and IkongUbong (Fluted Pumpkins) amongst others.

Socio-Cultural Life

The community is cheerful and hospitable to strangers. The people are socialized by their respective families to maintain a high moral standard. This morality manifests in respect for parents, elders and the aged. Regard for elders is predicated on a number of cherished convictions which include the notion that “OsongOwoOsongoIfiok (the older, the wiser). Cultural folklore, riddles, songs, dances and masquerades provided socio-cultural platform for interaction, education and recreation in the community.

There are other socio-cultural institutions such as secret societies which performed great social, religious, humanitarian and moral functions in the pre-colonial era. Due to Western influence, these institutions have dwindling reputation as vital agencies of law enforcement. They include Ekpe, Ekpo, and Obon. However, there are some instruments for regulating social relations that have survived despite Western influence. They include Mbiam (Oaths), Idiong (divination), Ukang (Ordeal), Ayei (Palm Fronds) and Nka (age grade/club). Again, ritual practices associated with the marriage of first daughters are still given important consideration.

Religious Life

The traditional religion and beliefs of Ibibio groups were based on the supreme deity known as AbasiIbom and lower duties (*mmendem*) who acted directly through the agency of the ancestors, chiefs and elders. Within the community, there is a system of belief in which the gods, the ancestors, and man interact freely within approved bounds for the good of all. Turaki (1999) asserts that gods and divinities play a significant role in determining traditional morality and ethics. Thus every Ibibio clan had its own deity and its worship entails special modes of behaviour prescribed sacrifices and

observation of ordinances (Esen, 1982).
The table below shows clans and their deities.

Ibibio Clan	Deity
Nsit	Anyaan
Uruan	Atakpo
Oku	Udu
Eket	Itauma
Offot	Ukana
Ibesikpo	Akasima
Etoi	Afia
Itam	Awa
Imam	Itina
Ikono	Etefia
Ibiono	Anantia

Source: Esen (1982)

The people of the community have a firm belief in life after death and also recognize their ancestors as the invisible member of their lineage. Thorpe (1991) affirms that this is a common belief among Africans whereby every members of the community including deceased ancestors and coming generations is closely linked with the community.

Theoretical Fraamework

The study was anchored on the theory of symbolic interactionism. Symbolic interactionsim grew out of the American philosophical tradition of pragmatism. Leading proponents of the theory include George Mead, Charles Cooley and Herbert Blumer. The theory emphasizes meaning, agency, and the interpretive analysis of interactional processes. The theory addresses how society is created and maintained through repeated interactions among individuals. Central to symbolic interactionist thought are the ideas that people act toward things on the basis of the meanings those things have for them. The attachment of strong social and cultural values on first daughter's marriage rituals reflects this understanding. Again, the theory assumes that the meaning of things is derived from the social interaction that one has with others. In the community of our interest, marriage is conceived as a community activity and the performance of traditional marriage rituals express this understanding. Symbolic interactionism focuses on communication, interpretation and adjustment between individuals in relation to the meanings of symbols. It states that our interpretation of a situation, and the meaning it has for us, is a precursor to our actions and behaviours. This implies that individuals are influenced by society and cultural norms.

Methods

The study was conducted in Ikot Oku Ikono. The use of qualitative method for the study was to facilitate the gathering of narratives and lived experience related to first daughter's marriage rites in the community. The use of purposive sampling techniques was preferred because it enabled the researchers to select participants who have ample knowledge and experience on marriage practices in the community. Face-to-face interviews were conducted to elicit responses from participants in order to gain insight on the phenomenon under study.

Results

Thematic analysis of qualitative data gathered through in-depth interview and participant observation resulted in the emergences of different themes related to marriage practices among the people of Ikot Oku Ikono.

Relevance of First Daughter's Marriage Rituals

Majority of the study participants expressed that there is a high level of socio-cultural value attached to first daughter's marriage rite in the community. In their narratives, they agreed that their forefathers had attached premium importance to first daughters because they were seen as mothers. Hence their departure from the household through marriage must be done symbolically to reflect these social and cultural values.

One of the participants had this to say:

Before first daughter marriage is contracted, a ritual practice known as “awaOduongo” (sacrifice and throw away) is observed. The whole exercise is known as mkpoadiahaowo (procedure for first daughter marriage). That must be done before a prospective husband could be welcome into the family. In some families in this community, the first daughter's family do not even want the suitor to show up until the ritual practice is done. Once the awaodoungo is completed, the suitor is free to enter the prospective in-law's compound and start proper negotiation for the actual marriage.

Another participant had this to say:

This is what we were born to witness. Our fathers attached great value to first daughter because she is like the mother of the house. So anybody that wants to take her away will have to fulfill these rites in honour and reverence to her position.

The data suggests that the first daughters, fondly called adiaha, is seen as a prized item by their parents and community at large, hence the placement of high value on her. Thus, the separation of first daughters from their families through marriage in this community is deemed a great loss. In view of this, for a man to marry adiaha, he has to adhere to these specified rituals.

Ritual Symbolism in First Daughter's Marriage

There are complex web of rituals relating to first daughter's marriage in Ikot Oku Ikono. The ritual acts do not merely move the individuals from one category to another but are expressive and symbolic enactments of the transformations.

During the awaoduongo ritual, the crowd is not invited. It is between the custodians of tradition in the first daughter's family. A pit is dug and the items will be sacrificed and thrown into the pit. The man and the prospective wife are not eligible to witness this. This procedure is done early in the morning before sun set. Those involved do not wash their hands before the ritual.

Another participant mentioned the requirement for awaoduongo. He had this to say:

Items for the ritual include: tortoise, sheep, squirrel, fish, which are all given male and female. Others are assorted drinks, kola, bitter kola, pepper, small pot, and currency.

A participant made the following comment:

After this awaduongo ritual, the man is free to enter the family and begin the process of marriage. So the first stage is the “ndiongoufok” (official entry into the prospective wife's compound). This is followed by the collection of list. But some smart people can negotiate and have the two processes at once. The man is given the list of required items for the

traditional marriage. He is expected to study the content and Bargain with the family in order to reach agreement. The first item on the list consists of mkpombup (requirement for asking for her hand in marriage). The items will be separated into the father's portion and the mother's portion. If the father of the woman is late, the man is required to slaughter a goat on the grave of the woman's father or join his right hand with the hand of whoever is slaughtering the goat. Then the blood of the goat will be robbed on the husband and prayer offered to bless the union.

Resistance to Awa Oduongo Ritual

The culture of a people is what makes them stand out distinctively from others in a family of humanity (Idang, 2015). However, human cultures are not static (Varnum & Grossmann, 2017). Cultural change is a result of several factors such as education, socialisation and resocialisation. Each of these factors has a specific way of altering the ways of life of a people. In Ikot Oku Ikono, education and resocialisation process of the Christian mission has culminated to impartation of new knowledge and values that run antithetical to the already established cultural systems. Most of the study participants reflected these rationales in their responses.

A participant said:

The church has challenged these cultural practices in recent times. Some people's involvement in Christian ministries has made them to see these practices as fetish and they try to dissociate themselves from the fetish practices of their father's household.

Another Participant said:

“The concern of some first daughters constitutes a resistance to the practice. Due to harsh economic circumstances, it is somehow different for men to afford to pay for this elaborate ritual. Because it could take up to N500,000 to complete awaoduongo excluding the main traditional marriage requirements. So many people avoid the first daughters see this as a source of marital stagnation and do not find this funny”.

A Participant said:

Some parents who are afraid that their first daughters might remain unmarried for a long time resort to collecting only the awaoduongo and overlook the main traditional requirements until when the man is financially capable.

Discussion of Findings

The study reveals that marriage occupies a pride of place among the people of the study area. The reason for this social value is found in the views of Ayisi (1997) that there is a link between marriage and family. The meaning of the term family as used in this context goes beyond husband, wife and children. It includes the departed souls, relatives and also the unborn children. The involvement of the souls of the departed in the activities justifies the view of marriage as a sacred affair. Also the traditional family thrives in the core values of traditional life. Again, this justifies the view of marriage as a family or community affairs.

Data from the Study show that ritual actions are engaged to help people to navigate the complicated route from singlehood to married life. Evidently, in some societies, important milestones such as marriage and adulthood are marked by ritualistic ceremonies (van Gennep, 1960). In Ikot Oku Ikono, culture provides for a ritual passage from singlehood to married life for first daughters. This corroborates the view that societies value children relative to their cultures (Aghajanian, 1988). Some of the features of cultural life of the people which survive Western

influences in some African societies are ritualism and traditional ceremonies. These activities are practiced to symbolise the cultural heritage and traditional value systems. People are expected to conform to whatever the society acknowledges as essential for their common good. It is this adherence to cultural prescriptions that ensures the perpetuation of the values, beliefs, customs and practices (Charles, 2005). Therefore the fostering of values is achieved through the immersion of individuals in the activities of the community. Over the years, first daughter's marriage rites and the myth associated with them are transferred from one generation to another to ensure continuity.

However, empirical evidence from the narrative of study participants have shown that Westernization and the activities of christian missions have some impact on the community in terms of transformation of traditional customs generally. Though some of the traditional beliefs still prevail, significant aspects of many hitherto valued customary practices have been eroded or at the brink of extinction. Data from the fieldwork show that though the custom of awa idoungo and awa adia are gradually being questioned by younger generation, it is still seen as relevant especially among conservatives, elders, custodians of tradition and practitioners of traditional African religion.

Conclusion

This study identified fundamental aspects of the culture of Ikot Oku Ikono that is still relevant in modern society. The study examined the social value of marriage rites and identified that marriage is regarded as a community affairs and could only be strengthened and legitimated through participation in various ritual activities.

References

- Udo, E. (1983). *Who Are the Ibibio?* Onitsha: African Feb. Publishers.
- Turaki, Y. (1999). *Christianity and African Gods: A Method in Theology*. Potchefstroom: Potchefstroom's University.
- Thorpe, S. (1991). *African Traditional Religion*. Pretoria: University of Pretoria.
- Esen, A. (1982). *Ibibio Profile*. Calabar: Piaco Press & Books Ltd.
- Phiri, K. (2011). *African Traditional Marriage: A Christian Theological Appraisal* Nairobi: Pauline Publications Africa.
- Olupona, J. (2014). *Africa Religions. A Very Short Introduction* Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Oduyoye, M., & Kanyoro, M. (Eds.) (1992), "Social Changes and Women's Attitudes Towards Marriage in East Africa. In the will to Arise women, Tradition and the church in Africa. M. A. Oduyoye and M. Kanyoro (Eds). New York: Orbis.
- Gehman, R. (2005). *African Traditional Religion in Biblical Perspectives* Nairobi: East African Educational Publishers.
- van Gennep, A. (1960). *The Rites of Passage*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
- Aghajanian, A. (1988). The value of Children in rural and urban Iran: A pilot study. *Journal of Comparative Family Studies*, 19(1), 85-97
- Oduyoye, M. (2004). *Beads are strands: Reflections of an African Noman on Christianity in Africa* New York: Orbis.
- Idang, G. (2015). African culture and values. In *PHRONIMON*, 16(2), 97-111.
- Varnum, M., & Grossmann, I. (2017). Cultural change: The How and The Why perspectives on Psychological science, 12(6), 956-972.
- Ayisi, E. (1999). *An Introduction to the study of African culture*: Nairobi, East African Educational Publishers.
- Charles, J. (2005). *Sociological Theory: A Historic Analytical Approach on man and society*. Lagos: Serenity Publishers.
- Noah, M. (1980). *Ibibio Pioneers in Modern Nigeria History*. Uyo: Scholars Press.